

THE IMPORTANCE OF INDEPENDENT WORK IN TEACHING SPECIAL SUBJECTS

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The article: describes the types of independent work in professional educational institutions, the procedure for their implementation and evaluation criteria. The students were shown an analysis of the results of independent work.

Key words: vocational education, independent work, personality, monitoring, cognitive, seminar

Today's reforms in the education system make students independent development of thinking, based on individual educational trajectories, creative in students to eliminate problems related to the formation of thinking and practical skills is directed.

The main task of secondary and primary vocational education is self the creativity of a specialist capable of development, self-education and innovation is to form a personality. In solving this problem, only ready-made knowledge transfer from teacher to student is not enough. The student is a passive consumer of knowledge to formulate a problem, to analyze ways to solve it, to obtain an acceptable result transfer to an active creator who is able to find and prove its correctness need Therefore, independent work of students is an important form of the educational process must be admitted.

How to do independent work in educational institutions is up to each student increases. In order to achieve success, the student himself is patient, from hardships he should not be afraid to work on himself. This is planned and implemented by the student himself increases. Problems in all aspects of society, changes in educational institutions affects the process of training students and sets new requirements.

First of all, it is necessary to clearly define what is the independent work of students.

Independent work of students is done by them under the guidance of the teacher, without his direct participation (but under his guidance) at a specially allocated time work to be done.

Objectives of independent work:

a high level of understanding of the educational material;

development of educational activity skills and competencies;
formation of cognitive abilities and interest in the studied material;
formation of readiness for self-education;
formation of independence as a quality of a person. Classification of independent work. For didactic purposes:

Educational materials. Such works are at the stage of preparation for the introduction of new material is carried out, i.e. after the explanation. The content of such works is reproductive is composed of character tasks and works are checked immediately. Independent to questions. By answering, students understand the teacher's explanation, the main thing remember features and rules, learn to apply them and are learning they receive the material with interest, because they themselves participate in its explanation.

Independent educational activities based on self-development of algorithms and algorithms includes problem solving.

Training sessions. Different objects and their characteristics for educational tasks includes recognition tasks. In these types of tasks, there are often some theorems, economic definitions and properties of mathematical objects should be multiplied or applied directly. This is independent study work from similar tasks that include important features and rules of definition consists of Strengthening. Contribution to the development of logical thinking for such independent work. Works that add up and require the joint application of various rules and theorems enters. How solid and meaningful they learned the educational material shows. Iterative, developing, controlling.

According to the level of independence of students, independent work is reconstructive and variable, it can be a partial search, research.

According to the example, they have preliminary knowledge of the studied object used for reinforcement. In this case, students have basic knowledge and skills and beyond the scope of reproduction activities aimed at mastering working methods does not come out. The proposed tasks are indicated by the teacher or in the textbook to detailed examples and algorithms is carried out according to.

At the reconstructive-changing level, students were new to themselves analyze situations, reconstruct them and use certain methods includes tasks that they should choose wisely.

Partial search systems are unusual, non-standard knowledge and skills requires transfer to situations.

Research projects Discover new information about the objects being studied to do, using the accumulated knowledge and skills, own hypotheses and designed to advance and test their judgments.

According to the level of individuality - group and individual. according to the source and method of learning - working with books, solving problems and drafting, laboratory and practical work, preparation of reports, etc.

according to the form of execution - verbally and in writing.

Classroom and home lessons by location.

Results of independent work:

collecting educational materials and his personal intelligence and assessment experience;

formation of development-independent work skills and abilities;

education-conscientiousness, perseverance, hard work, discipline, responsibility, etc

educate.;

diagnostic - student's acquisition of knowledge, skills and intellectual and physical shows the development of strength and abilities. Organization of independent work outside the classroom.

Recently, in secondary and primary vocational education institutions the number of class hours allocated for studying mathematics and economics has been reduced, and the content did not decrease, and in some sections it even expanded. This attitude with vocational schools and educational standards for independent work of students significantly increased the time standards for Develop a working curriculum for science the teacher also explains the content of independent work outside the classroom plans. At the same time, each student has mathematical knowledge and independent work it is necessary to organize in such a way that it will be possible to acquire economic skills.

Teacher before students do independent work outside of class gives instructions on the execution of the task, in which the purpose of the task, its content, terms, estimated scope of work, basic requirements for work results and evaluation criteria are available. Sometimes the teacher confronts the students during the assignment about common errors that may occur warns. Instruction is provided by the teacher for learning the subject given on account of time. Independent work goal, scope, specific topic of independent work, level of difficulty and perform individually or in groups of students depending on the skill level of the students can be increased.

Monitoring the results of students' extracurricular independent work is a science Compulsory classes and extracurricular activities of students in science can be done in the time allocated for independent work, written, orally or it can be conducted in a mixed form.

From seminars, tests, reports, etc. to students' extracurricular activities can be used as forms and methods of monitoring independent work.

Criteria for evaluating the results of the student's extracurricular independent work:

- level of development of educational material by the student;
- the student's ability to use theoretical knowledge in performing practical tasks;
- formation of general academic skills;
- authenticity and clarity of the answer;
- designing material according to requirements.

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